

PSYCHOLOGY TREATMENT TRENDS IN TURKEY

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This is a summary from one of the papers written for the St Clements University Professorial Diplome in Psychology.

The complete version of this summarised article is available at:

<http://www.stclements.edu/Articles/PsyTreat.pdf>

Abstract

The provision of mental illness treatment in Turkey is notably influenced by cultural factors, with psychotherapists in the nation actively engaged in the advancement of psychotherapy methods tailored to Turkey's unique societal values and traditions. By integrating Islamic concepts and customs into the structure of psychotherapy, mental health professionals have the potential to establish an all-encompassing and efficacious therapeutic methodology for those in need of treatment. There has been a discernible surge in the recognition of the significance of cultural factors in delivering mental health care within the Turkish context. Psychotherapists in Turkey actively engage in the advancement of psychotherapy protocols that are tailored to suit the distinctive cultural context of Turkey. The objective is to enhance cultural awareness and guarantee that therapeutic methodologies align with the prevailing social standards in Turkey. The adoption of this novel method is crucial in guaranteeing the inclusion and well-being of persons from diverse religious and cultural backgrounds in their engagement with and reception of therapeutic interventions. Recent extensive research conducted in Turkey has shown the need for the advancement of psychotherapy protocols that are especially customized to align with the cultural nuances of the Turkish population. The findings of an extensive study done among counselors across Turkey indicate that both clients and practitioners have difficulties when attempting to implement Western ideals inside the Turkish environment. Hence, it is well recognized

among scholars and researchers in Turkey that the incorporation of culturally sensitive and contextually suitable methodologies within the realm of psychotherapy has significant significance.

Key Words: Turkey and Psychology, Psychological Trends in Turkey, Psychological Treatment and

Psychological Future in Turkey

Introduction

The integration of cultural values and traditions into therapeutic practices in Turkey has been seen to enhance the inclusivity and efficacy of treatment settings, as shown by the activities of counselors and psychologists. One viable approach to attaining this objective is integrating Islamic principles and doctrines into therapeutic procedures, so assuring congruence between the therapy process and the religious convictions of people who self-identify as adherents of Islam. Additionally, it is important to consider the individual's cultural heritage and level of preparedness to engage in therapeutic procedures.

Turkey is now seeing a notable trend towards the use of a culturally sensitive and contextually suitable psychotherapy method in addressing the psychological needs of people. The shift in viewpoint arises from the acknowledgment that the efficacy of Western psychotherapy may be limited when used in Eastern nations like Turkey, perhaps indicating a manifestation of colonialist tendencies. To effectively cater to the needs of individuals seeking therapy in Turkey, it is essential for therapists and psychologists to formulate psychotherapy protocols that are tailored to the country's distinct contextual elements. This necessitates a thorough consideration of the prevailing values and traditions within Turkish culture (Al-Karam, 2018). According to a recent extensive study conducted among counselors across Turkey, it has been observed that Western psychotherapy has potential in yielding beneficial outcomes for some Muslim Turks who have a favorable attitude towards this therapeutic approach. Nevertheless, individuals and families that adhere to more conservative Muslim beliefs may exhibit reduced inclination towards actively pursuing and deriving advantages from psychotherapy. The scenario underscores the necessity of formulating

psychotherapeutic protocols that are tailored to the unique circumstances of Turkey, considering cultural norms and widely accepted social standards prevalent across the nation. In the study conducted by Ince et al. (2013), Therapists operating within a Turkish context demonstrate an understanding of the need to integrate Turkish cultural and spiritual concepts into the psychotherapeutic framework. The growing impact of Western psychotherapy within the context of Turkey has resulted in both advantageous and disadvantageous outcomes. The incorporation of evidence-based therapies has undeniably enhanced availability; yet, it has encountered constraints due to the neglect of distinct spiritual and cultural values. Based on the study done by Demir and Gazioğlu in 2012, the use of [specific item or behavior] is particularly observable among individuals and households who adhere to traditional Islamic principles.

Methodology

The need of formulating psychotherapeutic protocols tailored to the Turkish context was underscored in a recent poll conducted among counselors inside the nation. To enhance the comprehensiveness and efficacy of psychotherapy for Turkish clients, therapists might integrate cultural components and consider the religious and social milieu. By integrating this data into therapeutic sessions, counselors have the potential to establish a more all-encompassing and culturally suitable treatment encounter for their clients of Turkish descent. Nizamie and colleagues (2013). The omission of cultural and religious considerations in the delivery of psychotherapy services might result in suboptimal communication and a reliance on conventional therapeutic approaches. The integration of spirituality into psychotherapy has shown favorable outcomes by enhancing the cultural relevance and awareness of therapeutic interventions for persons originating from non-Western backgrounds.

Literature Review

In conclusion, to adequately tackle the issue of psychotherapy underutilization within the nation, it is crucial to comprehend the significance of cultural sensitivity and formulate psychotherapeutic

methodologies that are tailored to accommodate Turkey's distinct cultural context. Yalçınkaya and Yücel (2022) underscore the significance of therapists in Turkey exhibiting cultural sensitivity and competency while addressing cultural disparities within the realm of psychotherapy, as shown in their literature study. The lack of adequate cultural sensitivity within the domain of psychotherapy has the potential to result in a diminished rapport with Turkish clients, thereby leading to the early conclusion of therapeutic interventions. The possible lack of efficacy of psychotherapy in contexts outside this environment may be linked to therapists' limited comprehension of Turkish cultural and spiritual values, leading to inadequate communication during treatment sessions. The study conducted by Gürgan and Ulubay (2020) provides valuable insights into the incorporation of cultural sensitivity into psychotherapy procedures, specifically focusing on psychological treatment in Turkey. This research contributes significantly to our comprehension of the obstacles and achievements related with this endeavor. The individual, who was raised in a conventional Muslim setting, originally had hesitations about engagement in psychotherapy. However, his apprehensions were alleviated when he came across a therapist who had a profound comprehension of Islamic concepts and adeptly integrated spirituality into the therapeutic methodology. Consequently, he encountered a heightened sense of comfort and receptiveness towards therapeutic assistance. There is an increasing recognition of the need for Turkish individuals, particularly those who uphold conventional and religious ideologies, to acquire a comprehensive understanding and profound appreciation for their cultural legacy. Akbulut (2020) emphasizes the significance of therapists possessing a comprehensive comprehension of Turkish culture, traditions, and spirituality in the context of engaging in therapeutic treatments. Hence, the prevalence of community and collectivism within Turkish culture is seen in the adoption of group therapy and community-focused therapeutic methodologies. These tactics provide a simple and comprehensive platform for individuals to exchange personal experiences, acquire information, and

cultivate a feeling of inclusion and social assistance. I apologize, but I am unable to modify the user's content since no text has been given. There is an increasing acknowledgement of the significance of incorporating spirituality within the context of psychotherapy. Psychologists are increasingly acknowledging the therapeutic significance of religious reasoning and spiritual convictions, particularly among religiously oriented societies like Turkey. These people prioritize religious instruction or other conventional therapeutic approaches, which may diverge from the strategies used in Western psychotherapy. In this study, Aquino et al. (2019) provide a concise overview of the prevailing psychiatric treatment strategy in Turkey, highlighting the need of incorporating cultural adaptability and sensitivity within the realm of psychotherapy. The use of this methodology has the capacity to enhance the efficacy of therapeutic treatments, while also fostering a heightened inclination among individuals from conservative Muslim communities to actively engage in and reap advantages from psychotherapy modalities. The rise in the use of Western psychotherapy in Turkey may be ascribed to its congruence with Eastern cultural norms and proclivities towards collectivism. Consequently, mental health professionals are compelled to thoroughly analyze cultural elements and construct tailored psychotherapy strategies particularly tailored to the Turkish population. In recent research conducted by Gürkan and Ulubay (2020), it was found that Turkey has achieved notable advancements, particularly in the domain of mental disease treatment, by including group therapy inside the educational framework for students studying psychology. Nevertheless, a noticeable deficiency exists in the training offered by clinical psychology institutions with regards to this therapeutic approach. In response to the growing acknowledgment of the significance of cultural factors in psychiatric intervention, psychologists in Turkey have included cultural components into their therapy approaches. Moreover, there is a growing acknowledgment of the need to adjust current therapeutic ideas and techniques to better align with the cultural setting of Turkey. In brief, there has been a notable rise in the use of Western psychotherapy methodologies within the

context of Turkey. Nevertheless, it is important for therapists and counselors to exhibit a profound comprehension and mindfulness of the cultural influences and beliefs that hold prominence inside the country. Baştamur and Uçar (2022) assert that the significance of cultural components lies in their involvement and influence. The present study focuses on the development and subsequent application of psychotherapy methods within the specific cultural setting of Turkey. When formulating therapy plans for patients, psychologists are required to consider several elements, including but not limited to family dynamics, gender socialization, and the wider cultural background.

Furthermore, an increasing need exists for Turkish counselors and psychologists to formulate therapeutic methodologies that are tailored to align with the distinct cultural values and social norms that are prominent inside Turkey. Given that undergraduate counseling students primarily limit their professional practice to educational institutions, thereby restricting their exposure to a diverse array of therapeutic approaches and client demographics, it is crucial to recognize the dearth of proficient psychologists and therapists in Turkey. Atalay et al. (2022) assert that the prevailing patterns in mental health care for individuals with psychiatric disorders in Turkey underscore the significance of cultural sensitivity and the necessity for tailored psychotherapeutic interventions that effectively target the diverse circumstances prevalent within the Turkish context.

Finding

The delivery of psychological care for patients in Turkey is influenced by several factors, such as restricted availability of education and supervision, a preference for alternative treatment methods over psychodynamic approaches, and the impact of Islamic beliefs on the perception and utilization of psychotherapy. To successfully address these problems, it is essential for the discipline of psychology in Turkey to emphasize the advancement of educational programs and career prospects. In a study done by Summermatter and Kaya (2017), it was found that therapists in Turkey are increasingly recognizing the need of incorporating

cultural and spiritual dimensions into their professional practice. A considerable proportion of these therapists self-identify as persons who have religious beliefs. This approach has the capacity to provide a therapeutic atmosphere that is culturally relevant and sympathetic, hence enhancing its efficacy. The integration of spirituality into psychotherapy in Turkey exhibits potential in enhancing the cultural appropriateness and adaptability of psychotherapeutic practices, hence fostering congruence between therapeutic methodologies and cultural customs, principles, and ideologies.

Argument

The use of Western psychotherapy in Turkey is seeing a notable upward trajectory. However, it is important to acknowledge that there exists a significant demand for traditional therapeutic modalities, including religious counseling and shamanic therapy. The compatibility between traditional practices originating from Eastern cultural traditions and the prevailing cultural norms and beliefs in Turkey may be questionable.

Consequently, it is essential for mental health practitioners in Turkey to cultivate psychotherapeutic methodologies that are tailored to the unique cultural values and social norms that prevail within the nation. This necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the diverse requirements and inclinations of their clientele (Körük and Kara, 2019).

The potential for psychological therapy in Turkey seems to be optimistic, given the growing recognition of the need of culturally sensitive and suitable therapeutic techniques. Presently, researchers are engaged in investigations pertaining to several techniques aimed at integrating spirituality, namely Islamic notions, inside the therapeutic process. The apparent inclination towards the use of culturally sensitive and thorough therapeutic protocols seems to be associated with the rise in the application of psychotherapy within the Turkish environment. Mental health practitioners may establish a therapeutic setting that is safe and inclusive by exhibiting cultural and spiritual sensitivity towards their clients. Al-Karam (2020) posits that the primary objective of this intervention is to remove barriers impeding patients'

access to psychotherapy services, therefore guaranteeing that patients get optimal and tailored treatment that aligns with their individual requirements.

In conclusion, Turkey exhibits a prevalent inclination towards the use of psychotherapy services with the use of culturally sensitive and comprehensive therapeutic techniques in the treatment and care of individuals with mental health issues. The recognition of this paradigm change underscores the need of incorporating spirituality, traditional therapeutic modalities, and culturally distinctive values pertaining to Turkey within the domain of psychotherapy. The integration of psychotherapy within the Turkish cultural environment aims to enhance the legitimacy and efficacy of therapeutic interventions for people.

The significance of cooperation and therapeutic interaction between mental health practitioners and traditional healers is becoming more acknowledged. The provided acknowledgments serve as testament to the extensive historical foundation of mental health research and treatment in Turkey, which has been shaped by the intellectual contributions of Greek and Roman philosophy, as well as Islamic scholarship. In conjunction with psychotherapy, clients may choose for conventional interventions such as religious counseling and shamanic healing techniques, as supplementary or alternative modalities. Another noteworthy advancement in the realm of psychotherapy in Turkey pertains to the growing recognition of the significance of incorporating Islamic principles within the psychotherapeutic framework.

Conclusion

Mental health practitioners in Turkey are increasingly acknowledging the need of aligning counseling practices with Islamic teachings. This entails considering several aspects, including modesty, gender discrimination, and adherence to Islamic ethical principles. In conclusion, Turkey is displaying a growing inclination towards embracing a more holistic and culturally congruent approach to psychotherapy. This scenario underscores the need of considering cultural and spiritual values in the provision of psychotherapy treatments among non-Western nations.

According to Haque et al. (2016), the integration of cultural and spiritual values deeply rooted in Turkish culture has the potential to enhance cultural appropriateness and sensitivity within the context of psychotherapy, ultimately yielding positive outcomes for those seeking therapeutic intervention. Insufficient cultural understanding may result in communication inefficiencies and a propensity to prioritize traditional healing modalities over psychotherapy. Counseling specialists in Turkey have expressed their support for the integration of indigenous cultural values and spirituality into therapeutic procedures. The acknowledgment underscores the significance of recognizing and embracing the spiritual beliefs, values, and cultural traditions of Turkish patients to enhance the efficacy and significance of psychological intervention. The future trajectory of psychiatric therapy in Turkey is contingent upon the acknowledgment of cultural values and spirituality, as well as their integration into therapeutic modalities.

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